

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This study reviews current composition on the part of motivation in alternate or foreign language literacy. Motivation is an important factor in explaining the success or failure of any complex work. In this composition, the experimenter identifies the term motivation, explains different types of motivation, reviews former exploration on the part of motivation mentions the terms of language literacy, motivation and eventually tells the main factors of motivation. Review of literature has shown that motivation plays a veritably important part in learning English as a foreign or alternate language successfully preface.

Key words. Communication, literacy , enjoyment , role , achievement .

Abstrakt. Ushbu tadqiqot muqobil yoki chet tili savodxonligi bo'yicha motivatsiyaning joriy tarkibini ko'rib chiqadi. Har qanday murakkab ishning muvaffaqiyati yoki muvaffaqiyatsizligini tushuntirishda motivatsiya muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ushbu kompozitsiyada eksperimentator motivatsiya atamasini aniqlaydi, motivatsiyaning har xil turlarini tushuntiradi, motivatsiya bo'yicha oldingi tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqadi, til savodxonligi, motivatsiya atamalarini eslatib o'tadi va oxir-oqibat motivatsiyaning asosiy omillarini aytib beradi. Adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish ingliz tilini xorijiy yoki muqobil til sifatida muvaffaqiyatli o'rganishda motivatsiya juda muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar. Muloqot, savodxonlik, zavqlanish, rol, muvaffaqiyat.

Абстрактный. В данном исследовании рассматривается текущий состав мотивации к альтернативной или иностранной языковой грамотности. Мотивация является важным фактором в объяснении успеха или неудачи любого сложного предприятия. В этой композиции экспериментатор определяет термин «мотивация», объясняет различные типы мотивации, делает обзор предыдущих исследований мотивации, упоминает термины языковой грамотности, мотивации и, наконец, сообщает основные факторы мотивации. Обзор литературы показал, что мотивация играет очень важную роль в успешном изучении английского языка как иностранного или альтернативного языка.

Ключевые слова. Общение, грамотность, удовольствие, роль, успех.

Introduction. Motivation is a kind of desire for literacy. To educate an alternate language in a literacy setting, the learners should have a desire to learn the language first. There are a number of factors that impact alternate language literacy. According to Dornyei (as cited in Kaboody, 2013) stated that motivation provides the primary motivation to initiate learning the alternate language and latterly the driving force to sustain the long and frequently tedious literacy process. Also, all the other factors involved in alternate language (L2) acquisition suppose motivation to some position. By giving sufficient motivation, it's stopgap that indeed individualities with minimum capacities can achieve long-term pretensions and a suitable class along with good tutoring will be sufficient to insure pupil achievement. In addition, high motivation can cover up for significant scarcities in both language chops and literacy conditions.

This is also supported by Gass and Selinker (2008) stated that a learner who's watchful about constituting numerous hassles to gain scrutable input is more likely to be successful in alternate language learning surroundings. A learner who expends the trouble for memorization (indeed if unconsciously) is more likely to succeed in either foreign or alternate language surroundings.

According to Pourhosein Gilakjani, Leong, and Saburi(2012), the success of any action is dependent on the extent to which persons try to get their thing, along with their desire to do so. Generally people relate to this cerebral factor – the impulse that generates the action – as motivation. It's a motive force that arouses, incites, or stimulates action. Motivation is an important factor in specifying the readiness of learners to communicate. Motivation refers to the combination of attempt plus desire to gain the ideal of learning the language plus desirable stations towards learning the language. That is, motivation to learn a alternate language refers to the extent to which the individual workshop or tries to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the pleasure endured in this task. trouble alone doesn't indicate motivation. The motivated person spends trouble towards the end, but the person expending trouble isn't inescapably motivated(Gardner, 1985). Motivation provides learners with an end and direction to follow. Thus, it has a crucial part in language literacy. Due to the lack of enough motivation, some difficulties may be for learners. Without desire to learn, it's veritably delicate for learners to gain effective literacy. As Huitt(2001) stated that paying attention to the significance of language will help learners ameliorate their motivation to learn indeed if they don't have enough natural motivation. It can be stated that preceptors should be apprehensive of significance of motivation in learners ' language literacy and through some changes they can help learners increase their motivation.The points of this paper are to define motivation, and eventually state crucial factors of motivation.

There are numerous different delineations for the term provocation. Elliot and Covington(2001), provocation gives the reasons for people's conduct, solicitations, and needs. Motivation can also be defined as one's direction to geste or what causes a person to want to repeat a geste and vice versa. Pardee(1990) said that a motive is what encourages the person to act in a certain way or develop an inclination for particular geste . Crookes and Schmidt(1991) define

provocation as the learner's exposure regarding the thing of learning a alternate language. Narayanan(2006) said that motivation is the reason or reasons behind one's conduct or actions. According to Gardner(1985), motivation is the combination of attempt plus desire to gain the end of learning the language plus favorable stations toward learning the language. Oxford and Shearin(1994) defined motivation as a desire to gain an ideal, combined with the energy to work towards that ideal. Motivation is the reasons underpinning geste Guay etal., 2010). Broussard and Garrison(2004) defined provocation as the trait that moves us to do or not to do commodity.

There are three crucial factors of motivation. They're positive station towards L2 community, the enjoyment of literacy, and external pressures. These factors are explained in the following section.

External Pressures. There are external pressures that motivate learners to learn an L2. Whether it's to please parents, admit a price, or fulfill some realistic points, learners are motivated to satisfy some external pressures. Noels etal. connect foreign and necessary provocation by stating that they both relate to the desire to learn a alternate/ foreign language because of some pressures or prices from the social terrain, internalized reasons for learning an L2, and/ or particular opinions to do so and their value for the named pretensions(2001, as cited in in Liu, 2007).

Enjoyment of Learning. If learners wish to be motivated they should enjoy learning the L2. naturally motivated learners are more likely to continue their studies than extrinsically motivated learners and simply share in an exertion for the pleasure of learning the L2. similarly, integratively motivated scholars enjoy learning the L2 and the culture of that community. There should be some kind of enjoyment while learning in order to be motivated to continue studying the L2(Wu, 2003).

Positive station towards L2 Community . Station towards the L2

community is veritably important in learning the L2. Gardner and Lambert(1980 as cited in Pae,) expressed that to learn an L2, one must have an station towards that community.

Conclusion. The below discussion reveals that provocation is a veritably important and effective factor in the field of learning language. therefore, the language preceptors and speakers should discover, realize, and pay attention to the personality of their scholars. also, they should be apprehensive of provocation, its high significance, and its types. They should also realize and get familiar with the character as well as the personality of each of scholars. latterly, according to that specific personality type, they should identify and fete the form of provocation relating to that and perform it in their tutoring process. In this case, they can have practical, useful, and effective langue classroom in addition to a positive outgrowth in their tutoring environment.

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